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Numerical Investigation on The Loading Methods and Size Effect for Compression Response of Braided Composites

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1. Outline

1. Background

2. FE-Model Foundation and Validation

3. Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

4. Conclusions

1. Background

➤ Fuselage

➤ Boeing 787

➤ Engine fan blade and containment casing

➤ Leading edge

➤ Lower wing cover

1. Background

➤ Accident due to impact

➤ Design approach

1. Background

➤ Textile composite

Woven

Triaxially braided

3D braided

➤ Mechanical response (Littell, 2008)

Axial strain of lay up composite

Axial strain of triaxially braided composite

Challenge: test, simulation

Experiment

Simulation

Out-of-plane displacement of triaxially braided composite

1. Background

➤ Damage morphology

Axial tension
(Kohlman 2012)

Transverse tension
(Chao Zhang 2013)

Axial compression
(Quek 2004)

Transverse compression

2.FE-Model Foundation and Validation

➤ Unit Cell definition

➤ Measure sample

➤ Generate geometrician model

13120
Elements

5096
Elements

1512
Elements

Cohesive element

fiber element

➤ Finite-element model

➤ Geometrician model

2.FE-Model Foundation and Validation

➤ Micromechanical model

➤ Constitutive model of fiber tow

Component materials

Property	Fiber	Matrix
Material type	T700	3266 epoxy
E_{11} (GPa)	230	2.5
E_{22} (GPa)	15	2.5
G_{12} (GPa)	24	0.96
St (MPa)	4900	89
ρ (g/cm ³)	1.8	1.2

Damage criteria

	Hashin's damage criterion	Current Model
Fiber tension	$e_f^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1T}} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{F_{LS}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)$	$e_f^t = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1T}} \right)^2 + \alpha \frac{1}{F_{LS}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)$
Fiber compression	$e_f^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1C}} \right)^2$	$e_f^c = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{F_{1C}} \right)^2$
Matrix tension	$e_m^t = \frac{1}{F_{2T}^2} (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{F_{TS}^2} (\sigma_{23} - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{F_{LS}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)$	$e_m^t = \frac{1}{F_{2T}^2} (\sigma_{22})^2 + \frac{1}{F_{TS}^2} (\sigma_{23}^2) + \frac{1}{F_{LS}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2)$ <i>(Hou, 2000)</i>
Matrix compression (matrix crash)	$e_m^c = \frac{1}{F_{2C}^2} \left[\left(\frac{F_{2C}}{2F_{TS}} \right) - 1 \right] (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{4F_{TS}^2} (\sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33})^2 + \frac{1}{F_{TS}^2} (\sigma_{23} - \sigma_{22}\sigma_{33}) + \frac{1}{F_{LS}^2} (\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2)$	$e_m^c = \frac{1}{4F_{LS}^2} (-\sigma_{22})^2 + \left(\frac{F_{2C}^2 \sigma_{22}}{4F_{LS}^2 F_{2C}} \right) - \frac{\sigma_{22}}{F_{2C}} + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{F_{LS}} \right)^2$ <i>(Hou, 2000)</i>

2.FE-Model Foundation and Validation

➤ Axial tension simulation

Fiber tension

Matrix tension

Fiber compression

Matrix compression

➤ Axial compression simulation

2.FE-Model Foundation and Validation

➤ Transverse tension simulation

Fiber tension

Matrix tension

Fiber compression

Matrix compression

➤ Transverse compression simulation

3. Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

➤ Compression sample with Size Effect

Finite element model of unit cell

3.Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

➤ Axial compression response with model's layer

3.Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

➤ Axial compression response with different size model

3.Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

➤ Axial compression response with model's layer

3.Meso-Scale Failure Analysis

➤ Axial compression response with different size model

4. Conclusions

- The three models with different mesh sizes show good consistency.
- Triaxially braided composite show different failure modes under different loading conditions. Free-edge damage is observed in transverse compression.
- The model under transverse compressive load shows obvious size effect.
- Future studies will be focused on introducing the boundary condition.

Current and Future Work:

- Improve the loading methods to make the model consist with test sample.
- Experimental validation.

Thank You !

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